

Interview Guide (With Software Practitioners)

Objectives:

1. *Ratios of Bangladeshi female farmers' values reflected in existing agriculture apps.*
2. *Strategies to address Bangladeshi female farmers' values in agriculture mobile apps.*

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Approximate Interview Time: 30-60 minutes

Introduction (By the interviewer)

1. Introducing myself (interviewer)
2. Explaining the research project
3. Explaining the interview structure
4. Giving the explanatory statement
5. Getting the consent form signed by the interviewees

Demographic Questions

1. What is your current role and the associated responsibilities?
2. How long have you been working in this organization?
3. How long have you been working in the software industry?

Questions on Values in Apps

1. In your opinion, what are the current impacts of mobile apps on society?
2. What impacts a mobile app should have on society, but currently are missing?
3. Particularly, what are the impacts of Bangladeshi agriculture apps (the apps you develop) on the users' lives?
4. Can you recall any feature that you think would make human life/society better? Describe the feature and tell us why you think it is impactful.
5. Which aspects/features of the existing mobile apps are (more) important for the female farmers in their personal life or make them, for example, happy, powerful, independent, etc. in their personal life? Why?
6. In your opinion, to what extent do the existing agriculture apps reflect users' values?

Questions on Strategies to Address values in Apps

1. How do you elicit the requirements and preferences of the target users (particularly, female farmers) of your apps before developing?
2. Do you have any mechanism/process (in requirement engineering, design or implementation) to integrate users' (particularly, female farmers) values in apps?
3. How does the software development process (which SDLC steps, responsibilities, roles etc.) need to be updated to meet the current demands for making impactful apps?
4. How do you collect the feedback of the users of your apps?

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5. How do you use the feedback to increase the satisfaction of female farmers?
6. Do you validate users' values in your developed apps? If yes, how?
7. How do you think the organizational culture should be changed to enable female farmers' values?
8. In your opinion, what are the challenges of collecting the values of female farmers' in rural Bangladesh?
9. What are the challenges of addressing their values into apps?
10. Do you have any suggestions on how to incorporate Bangladeshi female farmers' values in agriculture mobile apps?